

HRP-AntiHRP Sea Star Primitive Antibody Complex in 3D

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Abstract:

Recently, CDR1 and CDR2 determining regions were discovered in the anti-HRP (Horse-radish peroxidase) primitive invertebrate antibody (IPA). In the same time 3D modelizations of this primitive antibody, were presented, in collaboration with EMBL (Grenoble, Hamburg). It seems interesting to show and it would be interesting to restudy the complex HRP-sea star anti HRP and this primitive antibody by the use of crystallisation and X-Ray observations.

Keywords: *IPA (Invertebrate primitive antibody), HRP, anti-HRP, Invertebrates.*

Introduction

Antigen-Antibody specificity was discovered by the use of recombinant protein (anti-HRP one) and revelation by Elisas (Leclerc, 2023). Secondly we clarified the existence of CDR1, CDR2, CDR3 in the sea star primitive antibody (Leclerc, 2024a). At last it was possible to modelize this last one in 3D by the help of Alpha Fold and Swiss models (Leclerc, 2024b). A first approach more or less significative was realized, a few time ago (Leclerc, 2024c): it needs again more implications from our side and those of partners I look for.

In Summary

Modelization in 3D of the IPA (Invertebrate Primitive Antibody) or sea star anti-HRP antibody with CDR1, CDR2, CDR3 sites were already published.

Another study shows, for the first time, an Invertebrate Ag Ab complex (Fig.1) and we retain the existence of contacts which can be seen, in 3D (Fig 2 and 3) Nevertheless further

studies are, of course, necessary to determine with more precision the nature of our primitive antibody (We think of crystallisation and X-rays analysis). IT is why I call for international help. We need also to measure distances between HRP and the sea star antibody and other parameters in this antigen-antibody complex.

Figure 1. HRP-SEA Star Anti HRP Antibody Complex. Ab in blue. HRP Ag in green

Figure 2. «Contact» Antigen in Green – Antibody in «Orange»

Figure 3. Other Contact between Antigen in Green Antibody in «Orange»

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